

A Quasi-Experimental Study To Assess The Effectiveness of Warm Mustard Oil Massage on Back Pain Among Postnatal Mothers Admitted In J.B.M.M Civil Hospital of Amritsar, Punjab

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Abstract

Childbirth is one of the most intense and significant experiences in a woman's life, whether it's the first or second pregnancy. A common challenge during the postpartum period is back pain, usually affecting the muscles and bones in that area. Hormones like estrogen increases at a significant level during pregnancy and then decreases after delivery. Rubbing warm mustard oil massage on back can improve blood flow and help to relax, which can reduce back pain.

The present study aimed to evaluate the effect of warm mustard oil massage in alleviating postpartum back pain among postnatal mothers admitted in J.B.M.M Civil hospital Amritsar, Punjab. The Experimental research design (Quasi-experimental) was selected for present study. Standardized Numerical pain rating scale was used to collect the data from sample of 80 postnatal mothers. 40 experimental group and 40 control group were selected using purposive sampling technique. For analyzing the data descriptive and inferential statistics was applied. The results of the study showed a significant difference in the pre- interventional and post- interventional level of back pain among postnatal mothers in the experimental and control group. The average difference between pre- interventional and post- interventional level of back pain was found to be statistically significant at $p < 0.001$ with 't' value of 40.26***df =39 in the experimental group and 17.75 in the control group. In order to find association of post interventional level of back pain among postnatal mothers in experimental and control group with selected demographic variables, analysis of variance was computed and findings revealed a significant association with age and Maternal BMI at $p < 0.05$ level of significance, whereas no significant association with Parity, Outcome of delivery, Baby's birth weight. In conclusion, warm mustard oil massage appears to be an effective method for reducing postpartum back pain. Therefore promoting its use can be beneficial for improving health and quality of life among postnatal mothers.

Keywords

Lower Back Pain , Postnatal Mothers, Warm Mustard Oil, Back Massage.

Introduction

Giving birth to a child is one of most intense experience of a life. It is the most unique experience every time whether it's the first or any pregnancy. A human body can bear only up to 45 Del unit of pain, but at the time of giving birth to new life a woman can experience up to 52 Del unit of pain. Pain in labour is considered as universal experience for childbearing women. Childbirth experiences may have some positive or some negative effect on women's lives and health. A positive experience can be remembered as an empowering life event that contributes to the personal growth of motherhood. A negative birth experience increases the risk of negative health outcomes such as postpartum blues, postpartum depression. There are three different types of delivery: vaginal delivery, assisted vaginal delivery (vacuum and forceps), C-section delivery. Even after giving birth women experienced several postpartum discomforts.[1]

Objective of study

The aim of the study is to evaluate the effectiveness of warm mustard oil in reducing back pain among postnatal mothers with a view to reduce back pain .

1. To assess the pre-interventional level of back pain among postnatal mothers in experimental and control group.
2. To assess the post-interventional level of back pain among postnatal mothers in experimental and control group.
3. To compare the pre-interventional and post-interventional level of back pain among postnatal mothers in experimental and control group .
4. To determine the association between the post-interventional level of back pain among postnatal mothers in experimental and control group with selected socio-demographic variables.

Review of Literature

The pleasant period of being a mother is felt after the birth of the baby. In addition to feeling happy, mothers also experience complaints that often become stressors. Discomfort is common for mothers during the postpartum period. Some discomforts experienced by mothers are fatigue, back pain, psychological problems, postpartum hemorrhage, and anemia.[2]

Postpartum is defined as the initial six weeks following childbirth. During this time, anatomical and physiological changes caused by pregnancy begin to reverse, and the woman adapts to the new or increased responsibilities of motherhood and life without pregnancy. Hormonal fluctuations during this stage can lead to musculoskeletal issues such as increased joint looseness. Women may experience a range of physical changes, lochia, perineal pain and as emotional adjustments.[3]

Postnatal period holds great significance in a woman's life. For first time mothers, it is often the most transformative and impactful experience they have ever encountered. This period is characterized by intense emotions, significant physical transformations, and the development of new or altered social roles and relationships. Women transition from being individuals to embracing their identity as mothers, marking a profound change in their social and personal lives.[4]

Need of The Study

The postnatal phase starts immediately after childbirth, typically spans six to eight weeks, and concludes when the mother's body has almost returned to its pre-pregnant state. It is critical to establish a reliable postpartum period that should be tailored into ongoing, continuous, comprehensive care. The care during the postnatal period influences the mother in her future life. Postnatal mothers are at risk of developing infections and complications if adequate care is not provided. Factors such as severity of pain during pregnancy, multiple pregnancies, and specific childbirth related factors may influence the duration and intensity of postpartum low back pain.[18]

According to WHO (2005) in the world 5,00,000 women die every year due to pregnancy and childbirth. In India 100,000 women die every year due to pregnancy as a child birth equating to one maternal case every 5 minutes. The morbidity of primigravida mothers after childbirth is estimated as 70 % of Indian primigravida mothers have sleep disturbances, 70-80% experiences baby blues, 76-82 % new mothers have emotional disturbances & 10-20 % of women with baby blues develop with postpartum depression. In India, 64% of mothers are suffering from back pain.[19]

Based on review of literature and also by the personal experience of an investigator during clinical posting in the hospital found that the main problem faced by almost all the women are back pain. There are various remedial measures used to reduce the back pain such as applying heating pad or hot compressors, kegel exercise, diverting and relaxation techniques and postpartum massage. Different type of oils are used for back massage like ginger oil, garlic scented oil, coconut oil, lavender oil etc.

Massaging with warm mustard oil is a simple and inexpensive measure to reduce level of pain, discomfort and promotes the physical well-being of mother. Investigator pre warmed mustard oil to approx 36°C, because in accordance with traditional care practices and to ensure mother comfort. This temperature closely matches normal skin temperature, facilitating optimal absorption, improve blood flow and relax muscles Hence, an investigator used warm mustard oil for back massage as an intervention.

Problem Statement

A Quasi experimental study to assess the effectiveness of warm mustard oil massage on back pain among postnatal mothers admitted in J.B.M.M Civil Hospital of Amritsar, Punjab.

Operational Definitions

Back pain: Persistent and newly developed pain in back after delivery. It also includes back stiffness and soreness.

Postnatal mothers: It refers to those who have been undergone Normal vaginal delivery and are admitted in J.B.M.M Civil Hospital Amritsar, Punjab. for atleast 3

postpartum days.

Warm mustard oil: It refers to mustard oil that has been heated to a temperature of 360C applied 8-10 ml twice daily for back massage

Back Massage: It refers to massaging the back by using technique effleurage, petrissage, friction and tapontment for 7-8 minutes to relieve pain and improve circulation

Methodology

The methodology is the most important part of research as it provides the framework for conducting a study. It outlines the general pattern for organizing procedures and gathering valid and reliable data in an investigation.

This paper describes the methodology adopted for "A Quasi-experimental study to assess the effectiveness of Warm mustard oil massage on back pain among postnatal mothers admitted in J.B.M.M Civil hospital of Amritsar, Punjab."

Sampling

Research Approach

The research approach involves the explanation of the plan to examine the phenomenon under study in a structured (quantitative), unstructured (qualitative) or combination of the two methods³⁶. In present study, the Quantitative research approach was used to examine the effectiveness of warm mustard oil massage on back pain among postnatal mothers admitted in J.B.M.M Civil hospital of Amritsar, Punjab.

Research Design

Experimental design (Quasi-Experimental research design) was used

E O1 X O2

C O1 O2

Research Setting:

This research study was conducted in J.B.M.M Civil Hospital of Amritsar, Punjab.

Target Population

Postnatal mothers.

Accessible Population

The accessible population for the study was postnatal mothers having normal vaginal delivery admitted in J.B.M.M Civil Hospital Amritsar, Punjab.

Sample and Sampling Technique

The sample size was 80 postnatal mothers. Purposive sampling technique was used for the study.

Study Variables

Independent variable: Warm mustard oil massage.

Dependent variable: Level of pain.

Socio-demographic variable: Age, Parity, Outcome of delivery, Baby's birth weight, Maternal Body Mass Index.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Inclusion criteria:

1. Primigravida and Multigravida.
2. Having mild and Moderate back pain.
3. Undergone Normal vaginal delivery.
4. Present at time of data collection.

Exclusion criteria:

1. Postnatal mothers undergone LSCS.
2. Postnatal mothers having severe back pain.

Selection and Development of Tool

The tool was adopted by considering the objectives of the study, reviewing theoretical sources, previous studies, exploring online resources, and through discussion with the guide, co-guide and after consulting with the subject experts.

Numerical Pain Rating Scale was used to evaluate the effectiveness of warm mustard oil massage on back pain among postnatal mothers.

Description of Tool

The tool was divided into two parts:

Part-A: Socio-demographic profile

This section consisted of items for collecting personal information such as age, parity, outcome of delivery, baby's birth weight, BMI.

Part-B: Numerical Pain Rating Scale.

This section included the Numerical Pain Rating Scale, ranging from 0-10 to assess the level of pain. The minimum score is 0 (No pain) and the maximum score is 10 (severe pain)

Validity of Tool

Validity indicates how accurately a research tool measures the concept it is designed to assess.³⁹ To establish the validity of the tool it was submitted for evaluation to nursing experts in the field of obstetrics and gynecological nursing, community health nursing, medical- surgical

nursing, mental health nursing, child health nursing. The tool was presented among panel members and the valuable suggestions were obtained.

Reliability of Tool

The reliability refers to the accuracy and consistency of the tool.⁴⁰ The reliability of tool was measured using the test- retest method and was found to be 0.86.

Permission for Data Collection

Before the data collection procedure, formal permission was taken from the relevant authorities of J.B.M.M Civil Hospital of Amritsar, Punjab. Written consent was taken from the subjects under the study.

Pilot Study

A pilot study is a miniature version of the actual research study, in which the research tool is administered to participants selected from the sample population.⁴¹ The purpose of the pilot study was to assess the feasibility of the main study. It was conducted from 14-02-2025 to 21-02-2025 at J.B.M.M Civil hospital of Amritsar, Punjab. Data was collected from 8 postnatal mothers who had undergone normal vaginal delivery. A purposive sampling technique was used to select the participants. Prior to the data collection, formal permission was obtained from the authorities of J.B.M.M. Civil hospital of Amritsar, Punjab. On the first day, a pre-test was conducted followed by the administration of back massage with 8-10 ml of warm mustard oil for 7-8 min twice daily. A post- test was conducted on 3rd day. The collected data was analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics including mean, standard deviation, t- test, chi square test.

Data Collection Procedure

Data collection refers to the systematic gathering of information during research process. In this study, Data collection was carried out during the month of March,2025. Prior to the process of data collection, formal permission was obtained from the Civil Surgeon of Amritsar and the S.M.O of J.B.M.M Civil Hospital Amritsar, Punjab. Participants was selected based on defined inclusion and exclusion criteria focusing on postnatal mothers undergone normal vaginal delivery. The purposive sampling technique was used to identify suitable participants. The researcher introduce herself to each participant, explained the purpose and objective of the study and obtained written informed consent. The socio-demographic profile was used to collect personal information while the Numerical Pain Rating Scale was used to assess the level of back pain. Participants were assured that all information provided would remain confidential and be used solely for research purposes. The pre-test was conducted from 80 postnatal mothers. Among them, 40 were assigned to the experimental group and 40 to the control group. The experimental group received warm mustard oil massage (Effleurage, Petrissage, Friction, Tapontment) for 7-8 minutes in which 8-10 ml of oil is pre warmed at temperature approx 36°C applied twice daily. On the third day a post-test was conducted for both the experimental and control group to measure any changes in level of pain.

Ethical Consideration

Permission was obtained from the concerned authorities of the hospital and written consent was taken from the subjects under study. Confidentiality of the study participants was ensured.

Plan for Data Analysis

Data analysis was carried out in alignment with the objectives of the study. It was performed using both descriptive and inferential statistical methods, including mean, standard deviation, t-test, chi square test. The analyzed data was presented visually using pie charts and bar diagrams to facilitate interpretation and comparison.

Result and Discussion

This paper entails summary of major findings with conclusion, limitation and implication of nursing practice, nursing education, nursing administration and nursing research. It also gives account of suggestions and recommendations for the future research in the field of obstetric and Gynaecological nursing.

Back pain is one of the major problem faced by every mother after giving birth to a child. This will occur due to pregnancy hormones that loosened joints and ligaments of women. This pain can last for weeks and even for months. Hormones like estrogen increases at a significant level during pregnancy and then decreases after delivery. This can be followed by back massage with warm mustard oil twice a day for 10 minutes in order to improve blood circulation and enhance relaxation.

Based on review of literature and clinical experience of the investigator, it is found that in many postnatal mothers, back pain can dominate feeling of motherhood and it has many negative impact on women's ability to care for their newborn.

In many hospitals analgesics were used to reduce the pain. Through the standard protocols are not available, still the literature supports the benefits of back massage with warm mustard oil to reduce the level of pain. The main aim of the study was to assess the effectiveness of warm mustard oil massage on back pain among postnatal mothers.

An intense review of literature was done to select appropriate methodology and tool for the study. In order to assess the effectiveness of warm mustard oil massage on back pain among postnatal mothers, a socio-demographic profile was

prepared, numerical pain rating scale was used. The socio-demographic profile of the tool was validated by the experts in nursing field.

Permission to conduct the study was obtained from the directors of selected hospital of Amritsar, Punjab. Pilot study was rehearsed before the final study project over a sample of 8 postnatal mothers (4 in experimental group and 4 in control group).

A Quasi- experimental research approach was adopted to conduct the present study. The sample was 80 postnatal mothers (40 in experimental group and 40 in control

group) who were admitted in J.B.M.M Civil Hospital of Amritsar, Punjab and were selected by Purposive sampling technique. Purpose of the study was explained to the postnatal mothers and written consent was obtained followed by pre- test. Back massage with warm mustard oil was given twice a day for two days and post test was obtained

The data was analysed using descriptive statistics - calculation of frequency, percentage, mean, standard deviation and inferential statistics - 't' test and chi square test. The data has been represented in the form of tables and bar graphs.

Findings

Sample characteristics

According to Age, in the experimental group (42.5%) of postnatal mothers having back pain were in age group 21-30 and in control group (42.5%) were in age group of 31-40 years.

According to Parity, both experimental group and control group (67.5%) of postnatal mothers having back pain were Multipara

According to Outcome of delivery, in experimental group (97.5%) postnatal mothers delivered a single baby and in control group (100%) of postnatal mothers delivered a single baby.

According to Baby's birth weight, in experimental group (77.5%) postnatal mothers delivered a baby weighted 2000- 3000 gm and in control group (85%) of postnatal mothers delivered a baby weighted 2000- 3000 gm.

According to Maternal Body mass index, in experimental group (47.5%) of postnatal mothers were Overweight and in control group (62.5%) of postnatal mothers were Overweight.

Objective-Wise Analysis

Objective 1: To assess pre interventional level of back pain among postnatal mothers in experimental and control group.

According to pre interventional level of pain, majority (100%) of postnatal mothers in experimental and control group had moderate level of back pain.

Objective 2: To assess post interventional level of back pain among postnatal mothers in experimental and control group.

According to post interventional level of pain, in experimental group majority(62.5%) of postnatal mothers had no pain and (37.5%) had mild level of back pain, whereas in control group (55%) of postnatal mothers had mild level of back pain and (45%) had moderate level of back pain.

Objective 3: To compare the pre interventional and post interventional level of back pain among postnatal mothers in experimental and control group .

The mean difference between pre interventional and post interventional level of back pain was found statistically significant at $p < 0.001$ with 't' value (40.26) in experimental group and in control group it was found statistically significant at $p < 0.001$ with 't' value (17.75). Hence was concluded that warm mustard oil massage had significant effect in reducing back pain among postnatal mothers.

Objective 4: To determine the association between the post interventional level of back pain among postnatal mothers in experimental and control group with selected socio-demographic variables.

The analysis of data regarding the association between the post interventional level of back pain among postnatal mothers in experimental and control group with selected socio-demographic variables of study participants. The results revealed that there was significant association with age and BMI whereas other socio-demographic variables like Parity, Outcome of delivery, Baby's birth weight had no significant association at $p < 0.05$ level of significance.

Conclusion

The study concluded that back massage with warm mustard oil is effective in reducing back pain. So it is important to encourage the use of warm mustard oil massage as a natural measure to relief pain among postnatal mothers to maintain health, functional dependence and quality of life.

Implications of The Study

The findings of the study have several implications for the nursing profession i.e in nursing education, clinical practice, nursing research, nursing administration. In these entire areas nurse acts as an educator, leader, counsellor, organiser, motivator and can help in making

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